

Pathological Studies on Metal Adducts of Oxytetracycline

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Amongst the various factors affecting the activity of a drug, its ability to form strainless chelate rings has been shown quite important¹. Further, it has been pointed out that certain metal complexes of drugs are proved more potent than the pure drugs². With this view, in this study, some metal complexes of oxytetracycline, an important antibiotic drug have been synthesised and screened for their activity towards gram-positive and gram-negative bacteria viz. *Klebsiella*, *Staphylococci*, *Pyocynus* and *E. coli*. The metal ions used for preparation of complexes include the essential trace elements, which are involved in a wide variety of biochemical functions in the body but most act primarily in enzyme systems. viz. Fe^{II} , Ni^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cu^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} .

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the metal complexes were found in agreement with the composition $[\text{M}(\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_5\text{O}_9)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}]$. A comparison of ir spectra of the drug with that of the complex indicates that the complexation of drug molecules has taken place through the

grouping. While the two characteristic frequencies of primary amide at 3 500 and 3 390 cm^{-1} are not changed, the stretching frequencies due to intramolecularly bonded OH group and that due to C=O diketone are very much affected. The stretching frequency of intramolecular H-bonded OH group³ which appears at 2 973 cm^{-1} in the drug is not observed in the complex while C=O frequency of β -diketone appearing at 1 615 cm^{-1} in the drug shifts

to 1 594 cm^{-1} in the complex³. Further, the C—O stretching frequency of OH group³ appearing at 1 045 cm^{-1} in the drug is shifted to 1 095 cm^{-1} in the complexes. These observations suggest the mode of linking of the drug molecules with the metal ion according to Fig. 1.

Fig. 1.

Bacteriocidal study: The results of bacteriocidal study with the metal complexes of oxytetracycline are recorded in Table 1 and Fig. 2 which show that some metal complexes are more potent than the parent drug. Higher bacteriocidal activity of certain metal complexes than the original drug may be due to the fact that complexation with metal imparts some important characteristics to the drug, which are helpful in its biological activity⁴. Which may probably be due to a comparatively faster diffusion of the metal chelate as a whole through the organism due to its more liposoluble nature. The higher biocidal activity of the metal chelate may also be due to the combined bioactive effects of the metal and the ligand and the higher concentration of the ligand in the chelate (1 : 2 M : L ratio). Further, the anti-growth

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANTIBIOTIC SENSITIVITY DATA OF SOME COMPLEXES

Compd / (Colour, m.p. °C)	Particle size	Standard Strains*				Strains isolated from patients*			
		<i>E. c</i>	<i>St.</i>	<i>Kl.</i>	<i>Py.</i>	<i>E. c</i>	<i>St.</i>	<i>Kl.</i>	<i>Py.</i>
$\text{Fe}(\text{Tet})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Black, 300°)	12.50	0	0	0	0	++	+	++++	0
$\text{Zn}(\text{Tet})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}^a$ (Black)	6.25	0	0	++++	++	0	+	++	0
$\text{Mn}(\text{Tet})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}^a$ (Brown)	6.25	0	0	0	0	0	+	+	0
$\text{Ni}(\text{Tet})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Green, 188°)	25.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	++	+
$\text{Cu}(\text{Tet})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Black, 325°)	2.60	++	0	0	0	++	++	+++	++
$\text{Cd}(\text{Tet})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Brown, 230°)	12.50	0	++	0	0	0	+	++	0

* *E. c* ≡ *E. coli*, *St* ≡ *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Kl* ≡ *Klebsiella*, *Py.* = *Pyocyanus*; (0) = Resistant, (+) = slightly sensitive, (++) = sensitive, (+++) = very sensitive, (++++) = highly sensitive. ^aM.p. >35°; all soluble in acidic water.

Fig. 2. Bacteriocidal activity of metal complexes of oxytetracycline against (●) *E. coli*, (Δ) *Staphylococci*, (×) *Klebsiella*, (○) *Pyocytnea*, (---) standard strain and (—) cultured strain.

(inhibition) of the bacteria species may be due to the exchange of trace metals of the metalloenzymes with the metal ions of the chelate under test and/or due to steric control of the encumbered and bulky chelate molecules. The results of present study clearly indicate formation of (M : L) 1 : 2 chelates with the involvement of O-atom in metal to ligand-bond resulting in a sufficient high covalent-nature of the chelate molecules and hence lipid-solubility.

The activity of a drug depends on its bioavailability, which in turn depends, apart from other factors, upon its particle size. It has been shown that reduction in particle size increases activity⁴. It increases the solubility of the drug and hence its bioavailability. In most of the cases the complexes having high activity have micro-particle size, which help their higher solubility (Table 1).

The specific-sensitivity of standard strains may be visualised in the light of the fact that drugs are enzyme-inhibitors and enzyme activities depend upon the presence of specific metal-ions⁴. Thus, in the present study it is seen that only a few metal complexes of a drug are more active (than the original drug) against a particular strain.

Further, the difference in sensitivity of a standard strain with its culture obtained from patients may be due to two reasons: (i) the patient has taken varying doses of some antibiotics before admission to the hospital and/or (ii) the individual resistance of the patient.

Mechanism of action: Tetracycline acts by interfering with protein synthesis. Its site of action is the bacterial ribosomes. It specifically bind to 30S-ribosomes⁵.

The results of present study show that the drug form complexes using the groups shown characteristics for their bacteriocidal activity (Fig. 2). Further, much higher activity has been recorded for

Mg^{II} , Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes (against the bacteria used in this study). As ribosomes are rich in magnesium ions⁵ hence these and/or the other active ions (Zn^{II} , Mn^{II} and Cd^{II}) may probably be involved in formation of a metal ion bridged ribosome-drug mixed complex resulting in the inhibition activity of these drugs. This, in turn, forbids the binding of ribosomes to m-RNA and results in death of the bacterial cell due to inhibition of its protein synthesis.

Experimental

All the chemical used were of A.R. grade. Pure samples of oxytetracyclines (Pfizer) were used.

Isolation of oxytetracycline complexes :

Oxyteracycline metal complexes were prepared by mixing solutions of metal and ligand in 1 : 2 (M : L) molar ratio and refluxing the mixture for 2.5 h over a water-bath. The solution on concentration gave insoluble complex, which was washed and dried under reduced pressure. The complexes were stored in air tight bottles.

Solution of oxytetracycline and its metal complexes were prepared by dissolving 125 mg of the drug or the metal complex (125 mg) in 0.5 N acetic acid (50 ml).

Biocidal studies : The studies were carried out in Pathology Department of Gandhi Medical College, Bhopal, using the standard methods⁶. The drug and its metal complexes were screened in vitro using disc-diffusion test⁶.

In each of the nine petri dishes containing the broth, the one impriginated with pure drug, the second impriginated with the solvent and the remaining seven impriginated with the seven metal complexes were placed. After overnight incubation, the zone diameters were measured. The studies were repeated with culture and the standard strains for comparison in each case.

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